

Intra- and inter-field compositional changes of oils from the Misoa B4 reservoir in the Ceuta Southeast Area (Lake Maracaibo, Venezuela)

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Abstract: Here we analyzed oil samples from 35 wells in the Ceuta Southeast Area (Lake Maracaibo Basin, northwestern Venezuela) in order to evaluate lateral intra-reservoir continuity in the Misoa B4 unit. Biomarkers, isotopic signature, and also V and Ni were examined using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), isotope ratio mass spectrometry (IRMS), and inductively-coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES). Multivariate statistical analysis was also applied to obtain useful information from geochemical data. On the basis of the characterization of these samples, we conclude that they all fall into various oil families derived from two pulses of hydrocarbon generation, migration and accumulation from the calcareous La Luna source rock, deposited in an anoxic marine environment under reducing conditions. Thus, these oils are a mixture of an earlier biodegraded, less mature oil charge and a later fresh non-biodegraded oil recharge. In addition, we applied asphaltene pyrolysis to one (LG-62) of the three “anomalous” oils. The LG-62 sample was confirmed as an almost “pure” paleobiodegraded end-member, whereas the VLF-3020 oil was tentatively classified as the unaltered end-member oil-type. Finally, the GC fingerprints and Fourier Transform Infra Red (FTIR) spectroscopic indices of the oils were used to detect minor variations in composition that are indicative of reservoir compartmentalization.

Keywords: Ceuta Southeast Area, Misoa B4 sands, reservoir compartmentalization, generation pulses, FTIR indices.

1. Introduction

The Lake Maracaibo Basin lies in northwestern Venezuela and covers approximately 50,000 km². The principal petroleum source rock is the Cretaceous La Luna Formation, although others also generated hydrocarbons (Talukdar et al., 1985, 1986; Tocco et al., 1997). The main petroleum accumulations are found in the Eocene and Miocene deltaic sandstones (Talukdar and Marcano, 1994). In turn, the region known as “Ceuta” is located near the Ceuta locality on the southeastern side of the Lake, 90 km southeast of the city of Maracaibo (Zulia State; see Fig. 1). The “Ceuta”

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region has been divided into various areas; one of the most important of these is “Area 8”, also known as “Ceuta Southeast”. This area covers approximately 70 km² and includes the following oilfields: onshore Tomoporo and Franquera and offshore Tomoporo (also named Lagotreco).

Figure 1

Previous organic geochemical studies (Talukdar et al., 1986; Murillo, 2008; among others) of the oils from the study area did not reveal great differences with respect to their origin and maturation, thereby suggesting that they originated from a mature marine source rock (the carbonate La Luna Formation). It has also been reported (e.g. Grobas, 2008; Olivares et al., 2009) that Eocene crude oils produced in the southeastern part of Lake Maracaibo Basin often show a very low content of saturated hydrocarbons and relatively high concentrations of resin compounds and asphaltenes. This composition could be explained by the fact that the medium to heavy crude oils produced in the aforementioned region are a mixture of an earlier charge of Eocene oil, which had been altered by biodegradation, and a later fresh unaltered oil charge originated from the same source rock (La Luna) during post-Oligocene times (Sweeny et al., 1990; Talukdar and Marcano, 1994).

Here we examined a set of 35 samples from oil wells in the Eocene B4 reservoir (~150°C) (nearly 5,000 m depth) of the Tomoporo (8), Lagotreco (19), and Franquera (8) fields. We addressed the origin, biodegradation, and thermal maturity of these samples and identified contributions of end-member oil types. Furthermore, we sought to determine intra- and inter-field compositional changes in samples and thus to evaluate lateral intra-reservoir continuity and, when possible, to delineate compartments in the study area. This information can be of great use for future EOR processes and petroleum geochemistry research in Ceuta and other eastern sectors of the Lake Maracaibo Basin.

2. Geological setting

The geology of northern Venezuela is conditioned by the interaction of the Caribbean, North American and South American plates (Macellari, 1988). In this general context, various authors

(Lugo and Mann, 1995; Parnaud et al., 1995; Mann, 1999; Castillo and Mann, 2006; Escalona and Mann, 2006; Mann et al., 2006; among others) have classified the sedimentary column in the eastern part of the Maracaibo Basin into several tectono-stratigraphic units: i) a Lower to Upper Cretaceous passive margin succession; ii) a transition to a compressive regime in the Late Cretaceous-Early Palaeocene, when collision and obduction of the Pacific volcanic arc overrode the South American plate and emplaced the Lara nappes; iii) a Late Paleocene-Middle Eocene foreland basin succession in front of the volcanic arc; and iv) a Late Eocene-Pleistocene sequence related to the collision of the Panama arc with the South American plate.

The southeastern margin of the Lake Maracaibo is bounded to the north by the Tomoporo fault, to the west by the Pueblo Viejo fault, to the east by the Moporo-1X structure and, finally, to the south by the R-5 secondary fault (see Fig. 2; Rodríguez et al., 1997). The Pueblo Viejo fault belongs to a group of normal faults originated in the Jurassic rifting (Roure et al., 1996). However, as it was reactivated as a result of the emplacement of the Lara nappes (Castillo, 2001), it is currently a N-S trending sinistral transform fault that dips steeply (70°) to the east. The Tomoporo R-1 and R-3 secondary structures (see Fig. 2) are E-W trending, 55° - 65° north-dipping echelon normal faults transversal to the main faults. Both structures were originated by extension during the appearance of the NW-SE outlying height located in the center of the current Lake Maracaibo Basin, within the period of active continental drift (Alcalá, 2013). The Andean uplift explains the inversion of these latter secondary faults and the emergence of the antithetic structures associated with them (Benkovics et al., 2000). As a final point, the Corredor 1, 2 and 3 faults, as well as the Moporo-1X faulting (see Fig. 2), are NW-SE trending and east-dipping transcurrent sinistral faults, generated as a result of the emplacement of the Lara nappes. Later on, compressive tectonic stresses in the region currently occupied by the Lake Maracaibo Basin reactivated and reversed these faults, thereby generating a flower structure (De Toni et al., 1996).

Figure 2

It is feasible that the faults described led to distinct B4 reservoir compartments in our study area, thus suggesting a subdivision into six blocks (see Fig. 2). Basically, Blocks I, II, III and VI are gently dipping homoclinal blocks, differentiated by dip angles and dip directions of rock strata. In particular, the strata of Blocks I and III show a NE-SW orientation and a 5-7° dip towards the S-SE (Fernández and Marcano, 2003). Regarding Block II, the homoclinal structure also shows a NE-SW orientation, but this block dips to the northwest (Lazarde, 2000), whereas Block VI (Franquera) is a W-E trending and steeply (3°) south-dipping homocline. Finally, two blocks (IV and V) are conformed by an anticlinal structure: Block IV with an anticlinal axis that has a SW-NE orientation and flanks dipping moderately (5-10°) to the NW, SW and SE, and Block V with a N-S axis trend and gently (3-5°) dipping flanks (Castillo, 2001).

The stratigraphic column of Area 8 essentially consists of sedimentary rocks from Cretaceous and Cenozoic ages (Fig. 3) and displays the following lithological characteristics, from bottom to top: Río Negro (coarse-grained, arkosic, and fine-grained sandstones); Apón (grey limestones and shales); Lisure (sandstones alternating with glauconitic limestones and shales); Maraca (biomicritic limestones); La Luna (organic matter-rich, black limestones and calcareous clays); Colón Formation (grey shales); Mito Juan (siltstones); Guasare (limestones and sandstones); Misoa (fluviodeltaic sandstones, limonites, lutites, and some limestone beds); Paují (grey shales); La Rosa (shales alternating with sandstones); Lagunillas (sandstones and carbonaceous shales); La Puerta (claystones, sandstones, coal, and conglomerates); Onia (sandstones, claystones and siltstones) and the El Milagro Formation—coarse-grained sandstones and conglomerates (Zapata, 2001; Linares, 2003; Palacios, 2006; and references herein). The Cogollo Group comprises the Apón, Lisure and Maraca formations (see Fig. 3). Detailed information on the Cretaceous and Tertiary stratigraphy of the study area was provided by Boesi *et al.* (1988).

Figure 3

The producing horizon under study is the Eocene Misoa Formation, which can be divided into several units termed, from top to bottom, Sands “A”, “B”, and “C” (Walton, 1967). The Misoa sandstones in all the units are massive and show good vertical permeability within each unit (Young, 1958). Subsequently, “B” Sands can be divided in nine minor intervals (B1 to B9). These horizons indicate a transition from a deltaic environment (B6 to B9) to a restricted coastal environment (Urbina, 2001).

3. Samples and methods

First, the 35 oil samples (see Fig. 2) were dehydrated with warm toluene (ASTM, 2004). The API gravity of each sample was measured using a Rice apparatus (ASTM, 2006). The concentrations of V and Ni were determined by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES) using a Perkin Elmer Optima 3000 sequential spectrometer. The sulfur content was obtained following the ASTM D4294-10 standard procedure (ASTM, 2010) by means of an energy-dispersive X-ray Panalytical spectrometer (Axios model).

Whole oil gas chromatographic analyses were carried out using a J&W Agilent PONA GC column (50 m x 0.2 mm i.d.; film thickness 0.25 µm; helium was used as carrier gas) in an HP-6890 Series instrument with flame ionization detection (FID). The gas chromatograph operating conditions were as follows: temperature maintained at 35°C for 15 min, increased from 35°C to 320°C at a rate of 2°C/min, and maintained at 320°C for 30 min.

An aliquot of each sample was fractionated into saturates, aromatics, NSO compounds, and asphaltenes (SARA method, Jewell et al., 1974). Briefly, asphaltenes were separated with *n*-heptane in a 1:40 v/v ratio using a Whatman’s No.2 filter paper following the ASTM D3279 standard method (ASTM, 2007). Asphaltenes were then purified several times by Soxhlet extraction with *n*-heptane until the liquid obtained was colorless. Soluble remnants (maltenes) were then fractionated

into saturated hydrocarbons, aromatics, and resins by liquid chromatography (De la Cruz et al., 1997). Aliphatic hydrocarbons were eluted with n-hexane, aromatics with toluene, and resins with toluene/methanol (70:30 v/v) using a column filled with silica-alumina. Later, gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis on saturated and aromatic fractions was performed using a HP 5890 Series II gas chromatograph and an Agilent 5973 N mass spectrometer, operating in “full-scan” mode. Helium was used as carrier gas. An HP-5 column (60 m × 0.32 mm i.d., 0.5- μ m film) was also used. The initial oven temperature was 50°C (held for 2 min), which was ramped at 2.5°C to reach 300°C and then held for 70 min. The mass spectrometer was operated in electron ionization mode (EI) at 70 eV. It was calibrated daily under auto-tuning conditions with perfluorotributylamine (PFTBA), and the chromatograms were acquired in full-scan mode (mass range acquisition was performed from m/z 45 to 500).

Carbon isotopic determination on saturated and aromatic fractions was performed using a Thermo Finnigan 1112 elemental analyzer coupled to a Finnigan Mat Delta C mass spectrometer. The reference materials were USGS 24 graphite, IAEA-CH6 saccharose, IAEA-CH7 polyethylene, and NBS-22 oil. The $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ ratio is reported in “ δ ” notation and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ refers to PDB (Pee Dee Belemnite). All analyses were performed in duplicate.

The asphaltene fraction of the LG-62 oil was analyzed using combined flash pyrolysis and gas chromatography with a mass spectrometer detector (Py-GC-MS) in full-scan mode. This analysis was carried out with a Curie-point Pye-Unicam pyrolyser—operated at 700°C for 8 s intervals—and the same GC-MS instruments were used although operational conditions were modified: 40°C (initial temperature) and final temperature of 260°C (held for 16 min). Fourier Transform Infra Red (FTIR) analyses were carried out using a Nicolet 20 SXB apparatus fitted with an arithmetic coprocessor 1240 and a TGS detector. KBr standard pellets were used, and spectra from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} were recorded with 64 scans and 2 cm^{-1} resolution. Preparation of the samples for FTIR

analyses and calculation of spectrometric indexes were done following the procedure described by Permanyer et al. (2002). Finally, we also considered previous data (Bracho, 2010) referred to the non-degraded single oil from a Cretaceous production well (VLF-3020) in the Area 8 (see Fig. 2). In regards to statistical treatment of data, a cluster analysis was performed using the SPSS 13.0 package for Windows. The centroid method was applied. The similarity percent was used as grouping parameter (Romesburg, 1984) and was obtained after calculating Euclidean distances.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Oil characteristics

4.1.1. Bulk geochemical data

The bulk composition, total sulfur, and API gravities of the 35 oil samples are shown in Table 1. Group type analyses indicated that the Lagotreco and Tomoporo (Area 8 South) samples present similar compositions: the aliphatic-hydrocarbon fraction (SAT) ranged from 30% to 37% (except LG-33 -47%- and LG-62 -24%-), aromatics in the 30-35% range (excluding LG-33), and a polar fraction (POL) between 27 and 34% (except LG-33 and LG-62 once again, as well as TM-33). The Franquera oils had an almost identical composition: 31-34% of saturated hydrocarbons, as well as slightly low resins plus asphaltenes (26-29%) and high aromatics content (39-41%) compared to most samples from the other two fields examined. These values are typical of apparently normal crude oils (Tissot and Welte, 1984). The API gravity varied from 18° to 20° for the Franquera samples, whereas most samples from (Lagotreco and Tomoporo) showed similar gravities of around 30°. Three “anomalous” oils (TM-33, LG-62 and LG-33 oils having 23°, 21° and 35°, respectively) have also to be considered apart. High sulfur contents (1.2-2%) were observed in all the samples.

Table 1

4.1.2. Carbon isotope results

The similar isotopic compositions of the 35 samples (whole oil, saturates, aromatics, and NSO compounds; see Table 1) suggests that these oils derived from the same source rock; in fact, the

standard deviations are close to analytical error (0.5‰). As shown in the Sofer diagram (Sofer, 1984; Fig. 4), $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values for the oils from the Ceuta Southeast Area indicate a common marine source of organic matter. Although these data must be interpreted with care as biodegradation and maturation may alter the carbon isotopic signature (Peters et al., 2005), this carbon isotope results do not seem affected by biodegradation and/or maturation degree as reported in similar cases (e.g., Beroiz and Permanyer, 2011).

Figure 4

4.2. Biodegradation of oils

Initially, and given the relatively low proportion of saturates and high contents of aromatic and polar compounds in all the samples (see Table 1), these oils may all have undergone biodegradation (Hakimi et al., 2011); for instance the saturate-to-aromatic ratio is below 1 in many samples. In addition, the results of specific gravity ($< 35^\circ$ API) also support the notion of biodegradation processes or perhaps the presence of a mixture of a more biodegraded crude oil and unaltered oil which arose as a result of convection or diffusion in the reservoir (Mason et al., 1995). This latter hypothesis about mixtures is coherent with the influence of two main events of oil generation and expulsion from the main source rock (La Luna) on the SE area of Lake Maracaibo Basin. These events implied a first charge of oil in the middle Eocene, which was later biodegraded at the end of Eocene after a basin uplift accompanied by an erosive period. Afterwards, a second charge with highly mature fresh non-biodegraded oil took place during the Neogene-Quaternary when the Lake Maracaibo Basin swung S-SE as a consequence of the initial uplift of the Venezuelan Andes (Talukdar et al., 1986; Grobas 2008), thereby burying the Misoa B4 reservoir once again. These two generation pulses may explain the presence of low API crude oils in the study area in spite of high API (35° and more) crudes as it could have been expected beforehand. In this regard, whole oil gas chromatography of the samples from Area 8 shows unaltered or slightly altered isoprenoids and a negligible loss of *n*-alkanes between *n*-C₁₀ and *n*-C₂₀ (see Figs. 5a and 5b).

Figure 5

Moreover, here we introduce the ratios biphenyl vs. triaromatic steroid 28R (BP/TA28R) and norpristane vs. C₂₃ tricyclopolyrenane (norPr/23T) for the first time to compare the relative magnitude of each oil charge in the mixed oils of interest. Notably, the paleobiodegraded oil reached level 6 or higher, according to the Peters and Moldowan scale, as shown by the presence of several 25-norhopanes and the absence of biphenyl or norpristane—the latter two usually degraded at level 5 of the same scale (Rowland et al., 1986; Peters et al., 2005). Therefore, on the basis of the observation of norPr/23T and BP/TA28R ratios close to zero (see Table 2), the LG-62 oil could be considered an almost “pure” paleobiodegraded end-member. In contrast, the VLF-3020 single oil (Bracho, 2010) may represent the unaltered oil charge.

Table 2

In this case, mixed oils with the highest secondary recharge gave the highest values of the two aforementioned ratios. Therefore, the novel graphical representation of norPr/23T vs. BP/TA28R shown in Figure 6 is useful to classify samples into the following two groups: i) Lagotreco and Tomoporo mixed oils (except TM-33, LG-62 and LG-33, which again are considered “anomalous” oils); and ii) samples from the Franquera oilfield.

Figure 6

Last, the presence of 25-norhopanes in the m/z 177 fragmentograms of the samples (Fig. 7a; peak identifications are in the Appendix) indicated a heavy level of biodegradation according to the scale defined by Peters and Moldowan (Peters et al., 2005). In fact, as previously reported in literature (see Lorenzo, 2014; PhD Thesis), the presence of 10-desmethylhopanes in our samples has not been associated with comingled production. Thus, we conclude that paleobiodegraded oil (Eocene pulse) was mixed with unaltered oil (post-Oligocene pulse).

Figure 7

4.3. Depositional environment and organic matter source

High sulfur contents and V/Ni ratios (around 8; see Tables 1 and 2) indicate that all the samples derived from source rocks deposited in a marine carbonate environment under reducing conditions

(Lewan, 1984). In fact, during the deposition of carbonate facies, bacterial sulfide is not fully sequestered by iron, and thus nickel ions precipitate in metal sulfides rather than form organometallic compounds. In contrast, stable vanadyl ions show the opposite behavior, leading to high V/Ni ratios (Escobar et al., 2011). Although V and Ni concentrations can be influenced by petroleum post-accumulation processes, the V/Ni ratio itself tends to be constant as a result of the structural similarities of organometallic compounds that contain these two metals (Lewan and Maynard, 1982). However, compared to the remaining samples, the TM-07 oil exhibited abnormal V and Ni concentrations, which can be explained by its high clay content (Lorenzo, 2014).

The *n*-alkane distributions for all the mixed oils were almost identical and typical of marine precursor organic matter (Peters et al., 2005): unimodal type with maximum peaks below *n*-C₂₀ (Fig. 5). Pristane/phytane ratios (Table 2) averaging 0.95 indicate that these samples were generated from organic matter deposited in a marine environment under oxygen-deprived conditions (Tissot and Welte, 1984). Although the relative proportions of pristane and phytane are governed by complex processes (Dzou et al., 1995 and references therein), the Pr/Ph ratio can be used here to indicate the depositional environment. As previously reported by Hunt (1996), the Pr/*n*-C₁₇ and Ph/*n*-C₁₈ ratios (Table 2) suggest that all the samples can be grouped into the zone that corresponds to oils generated from mature type II kerogen (Fig. 8a). In addition, both the dibenzothiophene/phenanthrene ratio and the total sulfur content (St) are used as paleodepositional-environmental indicators of sedimentary rocks (Hughes et al., 1995). In this context, all our samples were found to lie within the marine carbonate/mixed marine field (Fig. 8b).

Figure 8

Biomarker distributions also denoted a common origin for all the samples. Figure 7b shows a representative terpanogram of samples from Area 8 (peak identifications of terpanes are provided in the Appendix). This *m/z* 191 mass fragmentogram displays a high relative abundance of the C₂₃ tricyclopolyrenane with respect to the C₂₄ homolog (see Table 2) and other counterparts, thereby

pointing to an organic matter source deposited in a carbonate marine environment (Peters et al., 2005). Moreover, C₂₆/C₂₅ tricyclopolyprenane ratios of around 0.8 (see Table 2) confirm that the mixed oils were generated from a marine carbonate source rock deposited under anoxic conditions (Peters et al., 2005). In these oils, the high abundance of tricyclopolyprenanes can be explained both by a high maturity of the second pulse (van Graas, 1990) and by the high degree of biodegradation experienced by the first one (Wenger et al., 2002). In addition, C₃₁R/C₃₀ hopane ratios exceeding 0.3 (see Table 2) are also indicative of oils deriving from organic matter deposited in a carbonate marine environment under reducing conditions (Peters et al., 2005). Furthermore, all the samples showed 18 α (H)-22,29,30 trisnorneohopane/17 α (H)-22,29,30 trisnorhopane ratios (Ts/Tm) lower than 1 (see Table 2), indicating again that these samples were derived from a carbonate source rock deposited in a reducing environment (Rullkötter *et al.*, 1985). Finally, given the preceding results and the fact that the marine-origin oils of the Lake Maracaibo Basin commonly lack oleanane (e.g., Talukdar et al., 1986), the presence of this non-hopanoid triterpene in our samples is inconclusive and could be explained by an exogenous input during petroleum migration and accumulation in the Misoa B4 reservoir (Permanyer and Salas, 2005). However, the interference of 25-norhomopanenes cannot be ruled out (Alberdi and López, 2000).

Figure 9 presents a representative m/z 217 fragmentogram of saturates (peak identifications of steranes are provided in the Appendix). The high abundance of C₂₇ regular steranes compared to the C₂₈ and C₂₉ homologs indicates a marine carbonate source rock (Seifert and Moldowan, 1978). Such a source facies for our mixed oils is also denoted by the low values (< 0.26) of the diasteranes/regular steranes ratio (see Table 2).

Figure 9

The relative abundance of the methyl dibenzothiophene isomers (MDBT) in all the mixed oils varied in the following order: 4 > 2+3 ~1 (Figs. 10a and 10b, peak identifications of aromatics are in the

Appendix). Thus, neither sample clearly showed the usual distribution pattern for the MDBT homologs corresponding to the carbonate lithology, with the co-eluting isomers (2- and 3-methyl) being the least abundant (Hughes, 1984). Although alternative explanations for this MDBT pattern cannot be dismissed, the most probable scenario requires a parallel 4-/1-MDBT rise with increasing maturation (Radke, 1988). Otherwise, additional explanations include a lateral change in source-rock lithology (Elrich et al., 1999) and/or selective water washing of the MDBT isomers (Galarraga et al., 2010).

Figure 10

4.4. Thermal maturity

Several molecular maturation parameters (bishomohopane isomerization ratio, methylphenanthrene index, and sterane isomerization ratios; among others) for saturated and aromatic fractions separated from the samples are listed in Table 3. Nevertheless, it must be pointed out that these parameters (perhaps with the only exception of the methylphenanthrene ratio) could not be applicable given the previously established mixture of a palaeobiodegraded oil charge (Eocene) and the fresh oil charge (post-Oligocene); that is to say, regular steranes, triterpanes, and triaromatic steroids were not fully removed in the first biodegraded oil (Peters et al., 2005).

Table 3

The bishomohopane isomerization ratios (%22*S*) showed an average value of 0.59 (Table 3), therefore all the samples reached the equilibrium stage (vitrinite reflectances exceeding 0.6%; Mackenzie and Maxwell, 1981). The sterane isomerization ratios (%20*S* and %ββ; see Table 3) rose from 0 to 0.55 and from 0-0.5 to 0.7, respectively, with increasing thermal maturity (Peters et al., 2005). Most of the mixed oils (except LG-62) showed %20*S* and %ββ ratios averaging about 50%, which would be indicative of a thermal maturity level equivalent to the onset of peak oil generation. In contrast, LG-62 oil displayed lower %20*S* and %ββ values (43%) than the other samples. Assuming that the LG-62 oil has a very low charge of post-Oligocene fresh unaltered oil, the latter values support a maturation level equivalent to 0.63% within the early oil window (Hunt, 1996) and

very close to the Eocene oil generation pulse. Also, all the samples showed $\delta^{20}\text{S}$ and $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ ratios with a strong positive linear correlation, suggesting vertical migration through faults rather than “geochromatography” during migration in the study area (Peters et al., 2005). This observation is in accordance with the literature (Talukdar et al., 1986).

The characteristic triaromatic (TA) steroid peaks were identified in the m/z 231 fragmentograms for the samples from the Ceuta Southeast Area (Fig. 11a). According to Peters et al. (2005), an useful maturity parameter (the TA ratio; see Table 3) has been applied in this case. Variations in the values of this ratio between most of the samples were relatively small (see Table 3). Most of the mixed oils showed similar values (about 0.4), thus corroborating the presence of mature oils in the Misoa B4 reservoir; however, LG-62 and LG-33 samples showed distinctive values (0.31 and 0.51), indicating lower and higher maturation levels ($\%R_{c1}$ about 0.63 and 0.82%), respectively, when compared to the other samples.

Figure 11

With respect to the methylphenanthrene ratio (MPR or ratio of 2- vs. 1-methylphenanthrene), this measurement is a valid indicator of the maturation level of marine organic matter only at vitrinite reflectances of around 0.9 (Radke et al., 1984; Cassani et al., 1988). In our case, all the samples showed very similar MPR values (1.18 on average; see Table 3), indicating a common maturity level equivalent to 0.93%. The almost identical MPR values can be explained by the higher susceptibility of 1- and 2-methylphenanthrene to biodegradation than the other two isomers (Bennett and Larter, 2008). Consequently, both 1- and 2-isomers would have been removed from the palaeobiodegraded first pulse (Eocene) prior to the appearance of the 25-norhopanes (Volkman et al., 1984). Thus the ratio could define with precision the maturity of the second pulse (Neogene-Quaternary). Moreover, this latter maturity level is coherent with that of VLF-3020 oil (MPR of ~ 1.2). These data, the other maturity parameters of the VLF-3020 sample (see Table 3), and the fact that our samples and this latter oil (see bulk geochemical and biomarker data in Tables 1 and 2)

derived from the same carbonate source rock (La Luna), lead us to tentatively propose that VLF-3020 represents the end-member of an unaltered contribution.

We also calculated the methylphenanthrene index values (MPI-1; Radke et al., 1982; Radke and Welte, 1983) for the mixed oils. These showed mostly MPI-1 values about 0.8 and therefore calculated vitrinite reflectances ($\%R_{c2}$) ranging from 0.77 to 0.83% (see Table 3 and Fig. 11b). These values denote maturation levels just before the peak of the oil window and they are slightly lower than those of the post-Oligocene oil charge (calculated vitrinite reflectance of ~0.93%). This latter observation is consistent with the predominance of 9-methylphenanthrene over the other three less recalcitrant homologs in the paleobiodegraded Eocene oil (Huang et al., 2004). Thus, as expected, the LG-62 sample displayed an abnormally low MPI-1 value of 0.55 ($\%R_{c2}$ equal to 0.73%) when compared to the remaining samples. Last, the dominance of Tm over Ts (see Table 2) may also indicate that the carbonate source rocks which generated the mixed oils of interest were thermally mature (Seifert and Moldowan, 1981). In this regard, the Ts-to-Tm ratio decreased in the following order: VLF-3020 > LG-33 > Area 8 South > TM-33 > Franquera > LG-62, which is consistent with the results obtained from the novel graph of norPr/23T against BP/TA28R (Fig. 6).

4.5. Asphaltene pyrolysis

Ion chromatograms for m/z 57, 142, 156, 178, 184, 192, and 198 corresponding to the LG-62 sample obtained after asphaltene separation and its Py-GC/MS are shown in Figure 12. Note a high proportion of the low-chain *n*-alkanes ranging between *n*-C₈ and *n*-C₁₄, typical of crude oils deriving from source rocks of marine organic matter (Peters et al., 2005). The lower abundance of methyl dibenzothiophenes with the co-eluting isomers (2- and 3-methyl), as well as DBT/P and Pr/Ph values of about 1 and 1.3, suggest a carbonate source rock deposited under oxygen-deprived conditions (Hughes, 1984; Hughes et al., 1995). Other Py-GC/MS results, such as the predominance of 2-ethyl and 2-methylnaphthalene homologs over their respective isomers and the 4-/1-MDBT

ratio slightly higher than unity, indicate that the pyrolysate and the LG-62 oil have approximately the same maturity levels (~0.6%) in the early part of the oil window (Radke, 1988; Peters et al., 2005). This feature is coherent with the fact that the LG-62 oil can be considered an almost “pure” paleobiodegraded end-member. In addition, the pyrolysate showed an abnormal MPI-1 index value of 0.65 (%Rc₂ of 0.79%), thereby corroborating that the MPI-1 index is not a useful maturity parameter for early mature oils derived from La Luna source rocks (Cassani et al., 1988).

Figure 12

4.6. Geochemical correlations

In an attempt to establish the La Luna Formation as the source rock for the oils from Area 8, we compared the geochemical data of our samples with those previously reported for several La Luna rock extracts from the southeastern coast of Lake Maracaibo (Talukdar et al., 1986; Murillo, 2008). Thus, taking into account the high sulfur content and V/Ni, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of oils derived from Cretaceous source rocks, the lack or near-absence of oleanane, as well as the distribution of steranes (C₂₇>C₂₈>C₂₉) and tricyclopolyrenanes (prevalence of C₂₃ tricyclic terpane over other homologs), we conclude that the La Luna rocks correlate very well with the mixed oils sampled.

To classify all the oil samples into one or various families, we conducted multivariate statistical analysis based on 20 variables (Pr/Ph, Pr/n-C₁₇, Ph/n-C₁₈, 22/21T, 24/23T, Ts/Tm, DBT/P, %22S, MPR, MPI-1, TA ratio, % $\beta\beta$, %20S, diasterane ratio, %SAT, %ARO, SAT/ARO, °API, %St, and V/Ni) by means of hierarchical clustering. The dendrogram plot in Figure 13 shows two clusters (Area 8 South and Franquera) and it was obtained from our experimental data. As expected, measurements of similarity within the family formed by all the Franquera samples corroborate their high similarity (cut-off of 0.01 in terms of Euclidean distance) using the proximity procedure (Everitt, 1993). Mixed oils from Area 8 South (excluding the “anomalous” oils: TM-33, LG-62, and LG-33) also showed high similarity.

Figure 13

4.7. Reservoir continuity within the Misoa B4 unit in the Ceuta Southeast Area

As previously mentioned, Area 8 can be divided into at least six blocks (Area 8 South I to V and Franquera; see Fig. 2) on the basis of structural features. Although all the mixed oils from this area are of the same origin (La Luna source rock), some of them presented distinctive API gravities and compositional differences (Tables 1, 2, and 3). Assuming that such variations in the samples could be partly explained by fault compartmentalization of the Misoa B4 reservoir and the relative amounts of oil accumulated during the Eocene and post-Oligocene generation pulses, several petroleum post-accumulation processes cannot be dismissed at 150°C (Philp and Mansuy, 1997). The light hydrocarbon distributions were examined for the mixed oils sampled from Area 8, following the method proposed by Kaufman et al., (1990). Figure 14 shows the n -C₅ to n -C₉ gas chromatograms for two representative samples (LG-78 and FR-03). In this case, the different toluene/ n -C₇ values (higher and lower than 0.2, respectively) and n -C₇/methylcyclohexane values (inferior and superior to 1) for samples LG-78 and FR-03 may indicate that water solubilization processes have a significant influence on Franquera API gravities (Thomson, 1987). Contrary to what might be expected given the lower relative magnitude of the Eocene oil in the mixed oils from the Franquera field compared to the LG-62 sample (see Fig. 6), the latter showed a slightly higher API gravity value (21°) than those for the Franquera mixed oils ($\leq 20^\circ$). This higher value might be attributable to the solubilization of petroleum components in water (Palmer, 1984).

Figure 14

We compared the whole oil gas chromatograms and selected six minor inter paraffin peak ratios in the region from n -C₅ to n -C₉. Some of these parameters cover the maximum difference of the peak ratios of the oil pool in our wells, others indicate water solubilization, and they all can truly reflect the continuity of the fluid of Misoa B4 reservoir in the sector under study. Therefore, they were plotted on star diagrams to establish similarities or dissimilarities between the mixed oils (Fig. 15).

Figure 15

The star diagrams shows the two main oil families related to Misoa B4 reservoir allocations. The first group comprises oils from Area 8 South, while all the Franquera mixed oils form the second family. The Corredor 1 fault acts as a seal between two separate reservoir compartments, impeding any communication between them. This observation contrasts with other faults (see Fig. 2) that favor reservoir continuity within the Lagotreco and Tomoporo fields. These results are in accordance with variations in the geochemical data for most of the samples. Moreover, the star diagrams of the “anomalous” oils (TM-33, LG-62, and LG-33) presented large similarities between them and with the other samples from Area 8 South. This observation is in disagreement with the notion that several molecular parameters and bulk geochemical properties for these three mixed oils clearly differ from one another and from those of the remaining samples from Area 8 South (for instance, 23°, 21°, 35°, and 28° -on average- API gravities). This contradiction could be explained by the similar chromatographic fingerprints for the mixed oils from Area 8 South being fundamentally assigned to the secondary recharge. As in other case studies (see Permanyer et al., 2007), gas chromatography fingerprints would have failed to identify reservoir discontinuities within the Lagotreco and Tomoporo fields. Thus we used an alternative tool, namely the FTIR method described by Permanyer and coworkers (2002), in order to provide evidence of compartmentalization within the Misoa B4 reservoir rock in the sector under study.

Last, we also applied FTIR spectroscopy to the 35 samples using indices previously reported in the literature (Guliano et al., 1988). Assignments of the FTIR bands were determined by reference to earlier studies (e.g., Permanyer et al., 2005). The aliphaticity, long chains, aromaticity and branched indices proved to be the most appropriate features to distinguish the mixed oils analyzed. Thus, the LG-33 and LG-62 samples showed the lowest and highest aliphaticity and aromaticity values, respectively, when compared to the other samples from Area 8 South (Fig. 16a). However, this diagram does not clearly differentiate between the mixed oils from each side of the Corredor 1 fault. In contrast, the results from a comparison of the long chains vs. branched indices (Fig. 16b) appear

to be more accurate to determine reservoir continuity, with five groups of samples being clearly defined. Oil samples from the Franquera field and Area 8 South (except LG-33, LG-62, and TM-33), respectively, form two homogeneous groups of mixed oils related to compartments separated by the Corredor 1 fault. These two families are coherent with those determined by the gas chromatographic fingerprint method. Finally, the LG-33, LG-62, and TM-33 mixed oils each constitute a group, thereby indicating the existence of permeability baffles and barriers within the Misoa B4 reservoir rock in Blocks I and III, with no connectivity between these three wells and the other wells in Area 8 South.

Figure 16

5. Conclusions

On the basis of our findings, we conclude that the mixed oils studied fall into two groups (except the three “anomalous” oils: LG-33, LG-62, and TM-33). Furthermore, we found that all the samples derived from two pulses of hydrocarbon generation and showed evidence of paleobiodegradation. All these oils also belong to the same genetic type and were originated from the same calcareous source rocks (La Luna Formation) deposited in an anoxic marine environment. In addition, we have tentatively established that VLF-3020 oil represents the contribution of the unaltered end-member oil-type. Petroleum accumulation in the Misoa B4 reservoir could be explained by vertical migration of hydrocarbons from the Cretaceous La Luna Formation to this reservoir through the faults that delimit the Ceuta Southeast Area.

Gas chromatographic fingerprints and subsequent star diagrams clearly reveal the barrier effect of the Corredor 1 fault, which defines two separate compartments (Franquera field and Area 8 South) within the Misoa B4 reservoir rock in the Ceuta Southeast Area. Nevertheless, reservoir discontinuities in the Lagotreco and Tomoporo fields can be assessed more accurately using the FTIR method, which denotes a very good homogenization of crude oils (except the three “anomalous” oils) across the faults that cut Area 8 South in Blocks I to V and horizontal

connectivity between sand bodies. Finally, the permeability baffle/barrier effect is present within the Misoa B4 reservoir rock in Blocks I and III, with no connectivity between the LG-33, LG-62, and TM-33 wells and the other wells in Area 8 South. These latter four oil groups are consistent with the results from several molecular parameters and bulk geochemical properties.

Acknowledgments

This study was partially funded by the Development Council of the University of Zulia (CONDES-LUZ), through the Research Project No. CC-0555-13. Authors thank Jesús Amaro† (PDVSA) for access to the samples and for providing geological information. We are also grateful to the two anonymous reviewers for their comments which helped us to improve the original manuscript.

References

Alberdi, M., López, L., 2000. Biomarker 18 α (H)-oleanane: A geochemical tool to assess Venezuelan petroleum systems. *Journal of South American Earth Sciences* 13, 751-760.

Alcalá, M., 2013. Evaluación de la unidad petrolífera B-1 de la formación Misoa entre las áreas de Franquera y La Ceiba occidente. BSc Thesis. Universidad de Zulia, Venezuela, 94 p.

ASTM, 2004. Standard Test Method for Sediment in Fuel Oils by the Centrifugation Method: Annual Book of the American Society for Testing Materials Standards, v. 05.01 and 05.02. West Conshohocken, Pennsylvania, ASTM International.

ASTM, 2006. Standard Test Method for API Gravity of Crude Petroleum and Petroleum Products (Hydrometer Method). West Conshohocken: ASTM International.

ASTM, 2007. Standard Test Method for n-Heptane Insolubles: Annual Book of the American Society For Testing Materials Standards, v. 05.01 and 05.02. West Conshohocken, Pennsylvania, ASTM International.

ASTM, 2010. Standard Test Method for Sulfur in Petroleum and Petroleum Products by Energy Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence Spectrometry. West Conshohocken: ASTM International.

Benkovics, L., León, F., Sarzalejo, S., Luna, F., Peña, A., Díaz, J., Sornes, G., Quintero, J., Morales, J., León, K., Helwig, J., 2000. Geologic structure and deformation sequence of the Barúa-Motatan area, eastern margin of Maracaibo basin, Zulia Oriental, northern Venezuelan Andes. Sociedad Venezolana de Geólogos, Caracas, Mem. VII Simposio Bolivariano. Exploración Petrolera de las Cuencas Subandinas, 150-160.

Bennett, B., Larter, S., 2008. Biodegradation scales: Applications and limitations. Organic Geochemistry 39, 1222-1228.

Beroiz, C., Permanyer, A., 2011. Hydrocarbon habitat of the Sedano trough, Basque-Cantabrian Basin, Spain. Journal of Petroleum Geology 34, 387-410.

Boesi, T., Galea, F., Rojas, G., Lorente, M.A., Duran, I., Velásquez, M., 1988. Stratigraphic study of the North Andean Flank. III Bolivarian Symposium: Petroleum Exploration of the Sub-Andean Basin. Caracas, March 13-16, 1-41 pp.

Bracho, E., 2010. Geoquímica de crudos cretácicos del lago de Maracaibo. MSc Thesis. Universidad del Zulia, Maracaibo, 187 p.

Boreham, C.J., Crick, I.H., Powell, T.G., 1988. Alternative calibration of the methylphenanthrene index against vitrinite reflectance: application to maturity measurements on oils and sediments. *Organic Geochemistry* 12, 289-294.

Cassani, F., Gallango, O., Talukdar, S., Vallejos, C., Ehrmann, U., 1988. Methylphenanthrene maturity index of marine source rock extracts and crude oils from the Maracaibo Basin. *Organic Geochemistry* 13, 73–80.

Castillo, M.V., 2001. Structural analysis of Cenozoic fault systems using 3D seismic data in the southern Maracaibo Basin, Venezuela. PhD dissertation, The University of Texas, Austin, 189 p.

Castillo, M., Mann P., 2006. Cretaceous to Holocene structural stratigraphic development in south Lake Maracaibo, Venezuela, inferred from well and three-dimensional seismic data. *AAPG Bulletin* 90, 529-565.

De la Cruz, C., Márquez, N., Escobar, M., Segovia, S. 1997. An improved chromatographic method for the separation of saturated hydrocarbons, aromatic hydrocarbons, resins and asphaltenes from heavy crude oils. 213th American Chemical Society National Meeting, San Francisco, April 13-17, pp. 416-418.

De Toni, B., Loureiro, D., Colletta, B., Roure, F., 1996. Structural Synthesis and Tectonic Evolution of the Maracaibo and Barinas-Apure Basins, Western Venezuela. Paper 90951 presented at the AAPG International Conference and Exhibition, Caracas, September 8-11.

Dzou, L.I., Noble, R.A., Sentfle, J.T., 1995. Maturation effects on absolute biomarker concentration in a suite of coals and associated vitrinite concentrates. *Organic Geochemistry*, 23, 681-697.

Erlich, R.N., Macsotay, O., Nederbragt, A.J., Lorente, M.A., 1999. Palaeoecology, palaeogeography and depositional environments of Upper Cretaceous rocks of western Venezuela. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 153, 203-238.

Escalona, A., Mann, P., 2006. An overview of the petroleum system of Maracaibo Basin, *AAPG Bulletin* 90, 653- 674.

Escobar, M., Márquez, G., Inciarte, S., Rojas, J., Esteves, I., Malandrino, G., 2011. The organic geochemistry of oil seeps from the Sierra de Perijá eastern foothills, Lake Maracaibo Basin, Venezuela. *Organic Geochemistry* 42, 727-738.

Everitt, B.S., 1993. Cluster Analysis. In: Edward Arnold ed. *Multivariate statistics*. London: Oxford University Press, pp. 42-50.

Fernández, E., Marcano, O., 2003. Diseño de pruebas de inyección de agua en las arenas B4 del yacimiento Eoceno B-Superior, Campo Ceuta. BSc Thesis. Universidad del Zulia, Maracaibo, 91 p.

Galarraga, F. Urbani, F. Escobar, M., Márquez, G., Martínez, M., Tocco, R., 2010. Main factors controlling the compositional variability of seepage oils from Trujillo State, Western Venezuela. *Journal of Petroleum Geology* 33, 255-268.

Grobas, J., 2008. Caracterización geoquímica y evolución del sistema petrolífero en el sureste de la Cuenca del Lago de Maracaibo. Tesis de Grado. Universidad Central de Venezuela, Caracas, 82 p.

Guliano, M., Mille, G., Kister, J., Muller, J.F., 1988. Étude des spectres IRTF de charbons français déminéralisés et de leurs macéraux. *Journal of Chimie Physique* 85, 963-970.

- Hakimi, M.H, Abdullaha, W.H., Shalabya, M.R., 2011. Organic geochemical characteristics of crude oils from the Masila Basin, eastern Yemen. *Organic Geochemistry* 42, 465-476.
- Huang, H.P., Bowler, B.F.J., Oldenburg, T.B.P., Larter, S.R., 2004. The effect of biodegradation on polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in reservoired oils from the Liaohe basin, NE China. *Organic Geochemistry* 35, 1619-1634.
- Hughes, W.B., 1984. Use of thiophenic organosulphur compounds in characterizing of oils derived from carbonate versus siliciclastic sources. In: Palacas, G. (Ed.), *Petroleum geochemistry and source rock potential of carbonate rocks*. AAPG Studies in Geology 18, 181-196.
- Hughes, W.B., Holba, A.G., Dzou, L.I.P., 1995. The ratios of dibenzothiophene to phenanthrene and pristane to phytane as indicators of depositional environment and lithology of petroleum source rocks. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 59, 3581-3598.
- Hunt, J.M., 1996. *Petroleum Geochemistry and Geology*, 2nd Edition, San Francisco, Freeman and Company, 617 p.
- Jewell, D.M., Albaugh, E.W., Davis, B.E., Ruberto, R.G. 1974. Integration of chromatographic and spectroscopic techniques for the characterization of residual oils. *Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Fundamentals* 13: 278-282.
- Kaufman, R.L., Ahmed, A.S., Elsinger, R.L., 1990. Gas Chromatography as a development and production tool for fingerprinting oils from individual reservoirs: applications in the Gulf of Mexico. *Gulf Coast Section of the Society of Economic Paleontologists and Mineralogists Foundation 9th Annual Research Conf. Proc.*, pp. 263-282.

Lazarde, N., 2000. Estudio de Factibilidad para la Inyección de Agua en el Yacimiento Eoceno B-Superior VLG-3729 en el Campo Ceuta, Area 8 Sur, utilizando Simulación Numérico. Tesis Grado, Universidad Central de Venezuela, Caracas, 101 p.

Lewan M.D., 1984. Factors controlling the proportionality of vanadium to nickel in crude oils. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 48, 2231-2238.

Lewan M.D., Maynard J.B., 1982. Factors controlling enrichment of vanadium and nickel in the bitumen of organic sedimentary rocks. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 46, 2547-2560.

Linares, R., 2003. Integración del yacimiento C-2/VLE-326/455 dentro del modelo geológico del bloque V Lamar, Cuenca del Lago de Maracaibo, Estado Zulia. Trabajo especial de Grado. Universidad Central de Venezuela, Caracas, 112 p.

Lorenzo, E., 2014. Geoquímica orgánica del petróleo en la región sureste de la Cuenca del Lago de Maracaibo (Venezuela). PhD Thesis. Universidad de Huelva, Huelva (España), 247 p.

Lugo, J., Mann, P., 1995. Jurassic-Eocene Tectonic evolution of Maracaibo basin, Venezuela. *AAPG memoir*, vol, 62, 699-725.

Macellari, C.E., 1988. Cretaceous paleogeography and depositional cycles of western South America. *Journal of South American Earth Sciences* 1, 373-418.

Mackenzie, A.S., Maxwell, J.R., 1981. Assesment of thermal maturation in sedimentary rocks by molecular measurements. In: J. Brooks (Ed.), *Organic Maturation Studies and Fossil Fuel Exploration*, Academic Press, London, pp. 239-254.

Mackenzie, A.S., Rullkoetter, J., Welte, D.H., Mankiewicz, P., 1985. Reconstruction of oil formation and accumulation in North Slope, Alaska, using quantitative gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. Alaska North Slope oil-rock correlation study; analysis of North Slope crude., Claypool, G. E., Ed., American Association of Petroleum Geologists, 319-377.

Mann, P., 1999. Caribbean sedimentary basins: Classification and tectonic setting from Jurassic to present. Caribbean Basins. Sedimentary Basins of the World, Elsevier, vol. 4, 3-31.

Mann, P., Escalona, A., Castillo, M., 2006. Regional geologic and tectonic setting of the Maracaibo supergiant basin, Western, Venezuela. AAPG Bulletin 90, 445-477.

Mason, P.C., Burwood, R., Mycke, B., 1995. The reservoir geochemistry and petroleum charging histories of Palaeogene-reservoired fields in the Outer Witch Ground Graben. In: Cubitt, J.M., England W.A. (eds.), The Geochemistry of Reservoirs. Geological Society of London, London, pp. 281-301.

Murillo, W.A., 2008. Caracterización geoquímica de crudos y rocas de las formaciones La Luna, Misoa y Colón en la zona oriental del Estado Zulia. Tesis de Grado. Universidad Central de Venezuela, Caracas, 126 p.

Olivares, C., Molina, A., Vargas, C., Espinoza, S., Hung, F., 2009. Regional model of petroleum charge, timing and preservation in the southeast portion of the Maracaibo Basin, Venezuela. Abstracts of 25th International Meeting on Organic Geochemistry, Interlaken, 436.

Palacios, C., 2006. Caracterización petrográfica de carbonatos del campo de Mara. Cuenca de Maracaibo, Estado Zulia. Trabajo final de Grado. Universidad de Zulia, 181 p.

Palmer S.E., 1984. Effect of water washing on C15+ hydrocarbons fraction of crude oils from northwest Palawan, Phillipines. AAPG Bulletin 68, 137-149.

Parnaud, F., Gou, Y., Pascual, J.C., Capello, M.A., Truskowski, I., Passalacqua, H., 1995. Stratigraphic synthesis of Western Venezuela. In: Tankard, A.J., Suárez Soruco, R., Welsink, H.J. (Eds.), Petroleum Basins of South America. AAPG Memoir, vol. 62, 681-698.

Permanyer, A., Douifi, L., Dupuy, N., Lahcini, A., Kister, J., 2005. FTIR and SUVF spectroscopy as an alternative method in reservoir studies. Application to Western Mediterranean oils. Fuel 84, 159-168.

Permanyer, A., Douifi, L., Lahcini, A., Lamontagne, J., Kister, J., 2002. FTIR and SUVF spectroscopy applied to reservoir compartmentalization: a comparative study with gas chromatography fingerprints results. Fuel 81, 861-866.

Permanyer, A., Rebufa, C., Kister, J., 2007. Reservoir compartmentalization assessment by using FTIR spectroscopy. Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering 58, 464-471.

Permanyer, A., Salas, R. 2005. Integrated thermal model, diagenetic history and oil correlation in the Western Mediterranean, Spain. Abstracts of IV ALAGO Workshop – Basin Modeling, Buenos Aires, October 16-19, pp. 1-5.

Peters, K., Walters, C.C., Moldowan, J.M., 2005. The Biomarker Guide: Biomarkers and Isotopes in Petroleum Systems and Earth history, 2nd edition. Cambridge University Press, pp. 1132.

Philp, R.P., Mansuy, L., 1997. Petroleum geochemistry: concepts, applications, and results. *Energy and Fuels* 11, 749-760.

Radke, M., 1988. Application of aromatic compounds as maturity indicators in source rocks and crude oils. *Marine and Petroleum Geology* 5, 224-236.

Radke, M., Welte, D. H., 1983. The methylphenantrene index (MPI): a maturity parameter based on aromatic hydrocarbons. In: Bjoroy, M., Albrecht, C., Cornford, C., de Groot, K., Eglinton, G.,

Radke, M., Leythaeuser, D., Teichmüller, M., 1984. Relationship between rank and composition of aromatic hydrocarbons from coals of different origins. *Organic Geochemistry* 6, 423-430.

Radke, M., Welte, D.H., Willsch, H., 1982. Geochemical study on a well in the Western Canada Basin: relation of the aromatic distribution pattern to maturity of organic matter. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 46, 1-10.

Rodríguez, I, Navarro, A., Ghosh, S., 1997. Nueva Frontera Exploratoria en la Cuenca Petrolífera del Lago de Maracaibo: Zulia Oriental, Venezuela Occidental. Asociación Colombiana de Geólogos y Geofísicos del Petróleo. Memorias VI Simposio Bolivariano de Exploración de Cuencas Subandinas, Cartagena, 565-581.

Romesburg, H.C., 1984. Cluster Analysis for researches. Lifetime Learning Publications. Belmont, US.

Roure, F., Colleta, B., De Toni, B., Loureiro, D., Passalqua, H., Gou, Y., 1996. Within plate deformations in the Maracaibo and East Zulia basins. Eastern Venezuela. *Marine and Petroleum Geology* 2, 139-163.

Rowland, S.J., Alexander, R., Kagi, R.I., Jones, D.M., Douglas, D.G., 1986. Microbial degradation of aromatic components of crude oils: A comparison of laboratory and field observations. *Organic Geochemistry* 9, 153-161.

Rullkötter, J., Spiro, B., Nissenbaum, A., 1985. Biological marker characteristics of oils and asphalts from carbonate source rocks in a rapidly subsiding graben, Dead Sea, Israel. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 49, 1357-1370.

Seifert W.K., Moldowan, J.M., 1978. Application of steranes, terpanes and monoaromatic to the maturation, migration and source of crude oils. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 42, 77-95.

Seifert, W.K., Moldowan, J.M., 1981. Palaeoreconstruction by biological markers. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 45, 783-794.

Sofer, Z., 1984. Stable Carbon Isotope composition of crude oils: application to source depositional environments and petroleum alteration. *AAPG Bulletin* 68, 31-49.

Sweeney, J., Talukdar, S., Burnham, A., Vallejos C., 1990. Pyrolysis kinetics applied to prediction of oil generation in the Maracaibo Basin, Venezuela. *Organic Geochemistry* 16, 189-196.

Talukdar, S., Gallango, O., Ruggiero, A., 1985. Venezuelan La Luna and Querecual Formations as petroleum source rocks. VI Venezuelan Geological Congress, Caracas, pp. 3606-3642.

Talukdar, S., Gallango, O., Chin-A-Lien, M., 1986. Generation and migration of hydrocarbons in the Maracaibo Basin, Venezuela: An integrated basin study. *Organic Geochemistry* 10, 261-279.

Talukdar, S., Marcano, F., 1994. Petroleum system of the Maracaibo Basin, Venezuela. In: Magoon, L.B., Dow, W.G. (Eds.), *The Petroleum System – From Source to Trap*: American Association of Petroleum Geologists Memoir 60, Tulsa, pp. 463-481.

Thompson, K.F.M., 1987. Fractionated aromatic petroleums and the generation of gas-condensates. *Organic Geochemistry* 11, 573-590.

Tissot, B.P., Welte, D.H., 1984. *Petroleum formation and occurrence*, 2nd Edition. Springer-Verlag, New York.

Tocco, R., Parnaud, F., Gallango, O., Alberdi, M. and Passalacqua, H., 1997, Geochemical modelling of the principal source rocks of the Barinas and Maracaibo Basins, Western Venezuela. *Bulletin of the Venezuelan Society of Geologists*, v. 22, p. 17-28.

Urbina, E.R., 2001. Determinación de registros pseudo-sónicos a partir de registros de resistividad en los campos Barúa, Motatán y Tomopoto. Trabajo Especial de Grado. Universidad Central de Venezuela, 153 p.

van Graas, G.W., 1990. Biomarker maturity parameters for high maturities: calibration of the working range up to the oil/condensate threshold. *Organic Geochemistry* 16, 1025-1032.

Volkman, J.K., Alexander, R., Kagi, R.I., Rowland, S.J., Sheppard, P.N., 1984. Biodegradation of aromatic hydrocarbons in crude oils from the Barrow Sub-basin of Western Australia. *Organic Geochemistry* 6, 619-632.

Walton, W.M. 1967. Contributions of the AVGMP Maracaibo Basin Eocene Nomenclature Committee: The informal units of the subsurface Eocene. Asoc. Venez. Geol., Min. Petrol., Bol. Inform. 10, 21-30.

Wenger, L.M., Davis, C.L., Isaksen, G.H., 2002. Multiple controls on petroleum biodegradation and impact on oil quality. SPE Reservoir Evaluation and Engineering 5, 375-383.

Young, G.A. 1958. Correlation of the Oligo-Miocene formations in the Districts of Urdaneta and Perijá, State of Zulia. Asoc. Venez. Geol., Min. Petrol., Bol. Inform. 1, 116-135.

Zapata, I., 2001. Interpretación sísmica estructural 3D y uso de atributos sísmicos en el Cretácico, bloques IX y XIV del Lago de Maracaibo. Tesis de Grado. Universidad del Zulia. Maracaibo, 129 p.

Figure 1: Sketch map of the Lake Maracaibo region showing the relative position of the Lagotreco, Tomoporo, and Franquera oilfields.

Figure 2: Structural map of the Ceuta Southeast Area, and situation of the study wells.

Figure 3: Stratigraphic column in the Ceuta Southeast Area. Note: source rocks (black circle) and reservoir rocks (black square). Depths are expressed in meters. Non-depositional periods shown by inclined lines.

Figure 4: Sofer isotopes diagram for the Lagotreco, Tomoporo and Franquera aromatic and saturate fractions.

Figure 5: a), b) and c), respectively, whole oil gas chromatograms for LG-78, FR-03, and LG-62 samples.

Figure 6: Plot of norPr/23T against BP/TA28R for studied samples.

Figure 7: a) and b), respectively, m/z 177 and m/z 191 ion fragmentograms showing 25-norhopane and terpane distributions for the characteristic LG-78 sample.

Figure 8: a) Relationship between Pr/ n -C₁₇ and Ph/ n -C₁₈ for samples analysed; b) sulfur content (% wt.) versus DBT/P. Note: I (marine shales), II (marine carbonates) and III (marine carbonates/marine mix).

Figure 9: Example of m/z 217 ion fragmentogram showing sterane distribution for the representative LG-78 sample.

Figure 10: a) and b), respectively, m/z 184+198 ion fragmentograms for the aromatic fractions of the LG-62 and LG-78 samples.

Figure 11: a) and b), respectively, m/z 231 and m/z 178+192 ion fragmentograms showing triaromatic steroids and for methylphenanthrene derivatives for the representative LG-78 sample.

Figure 12: a), b), c) and d), respectively, distribution patterns of the paraffin hydrocarbons, naphthalene series, phenanthrene compounds, and dibenzothiophenes for the product obtained by pyrolysis of the LG-62 sample.

Figure 13: Dendrogram showing the clustering of sampling wells.

Figure 14: Gas chromatogram fingerprints from n -C₅ to n -C₉ for representative FR-03 and LG-78 oils showing the peaks selected to calculate all the ratios A to F plotted on star diagrams.

Figure 15: Star diagrams of the samples FR-03, LG-78, LG-33, LG-62, TM-11 and TM-33. Note the use of the six pairs of components (A to F) in the order given: n -heptane to toluene ratio, benzene to 1,1-dimethylcyclopentane, n -heptane to methylcyclohexane, 2t-ethylmethylcyclopentane to 1t,2-dimethylcyclohexane, 2,6-dimethylheptane to 1,1,3-trimethylcyclohexane, as well as m -xylene to 4-methyloctane.

Figure 16: a) and b), Aromaticity versus aliphaticity and long chains rate versus branched index diagrams for the crude oils analyzed.